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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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GENETIK MODIFIKATSIYALANGAN MAHSULOTLAR VA ULARNING INSON SALOMATLIGIGA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya: Genetik modifikatsiyalangan organizmlar (GMO) zamonaviy biotexnologiyaning muhim yutuqlaridan biri bo'lib, ular qishloq xo'jaligida hosildorlikni oshirish, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlash shuningdek ekologik zararlarni kamaytirish kabi maqsadlarda qo'llaniladi. Biroq, hozirgi kunda GMO mahsulotlarining inson salomatligiga ta'siri haqida turli ilmiy fikrlar mavjud. Ba'zi tadqiqotlar GMO mahsulotlarining allergik reaksiyalar, toksik ta'sirlar va antibiotiklarga chidamli bakteriyalarning rivojlanishiga olib kelishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Ushbu maqolada GMO mahsulotlarining inson organizmiga nisbatan ijobiy va salbiy ta'siri ilmiy manbalar asosida tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: GMO, genetik modifikatsiya, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, ekologiya, biotexnologiya, allergiya, pestitsidlar, Beta-karotin, Golden Rice.

Hozirgi kunga kelib, genetik modifikatsiyalangan organizmlar (GMO) zamonaviy qishloq xo'jaligi va oziq-ovqat sanoatining muhim bir qismiga aylanib ulgurgan. GMO mahsulotlar hosildorlikni oshirish, zararkunandalarga chidamlilikni kuchaytirish va oziq-ovqat sifatini yaxshilash uchun yaratilgan bo'lsada, ularning inson salomatligiga ta'siri bo'yicha global miqyosda bahs va munozaralar olib borilmoqda. Shu boisdan, dunyo miqyosida GMO mahsulotlari inson salomatligiga ta'sirini o'rganish bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlarning natijalari jamlandi.

1990-yilda ishlab chiqilgan "Oltin guruch" (Golden Rice) loyihasi shunday tadqiqotlardan biri bo'lib, Ingo Potrykus va Peter Beyer tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan. Ushbu loyiha inson salomatligini yaxshilash maqsadida oddiy guruch tarkibiga beta-karotin ishlab chiqarish uchun genetik modifikatsiya kiritishga asoslangan. Beta-karotin inson organizmida A vitaminiga aylanadi, bu esa ko'rish qobiliyatini saqlash va immun tizimini mustahkamlashga yordam beradi [1].

GMO texnologiyalarining yana bir muhim natijalaridan biri "Bt-makkajo'xori loyihasi" hisoblanadi. Ushbu loyiha zararkunandalarga chidamli makkajo'xori navlarini yaratishga qaratilgan bo'lib, u 2002-yilda John Shelton va 2010-yilda AQSH olimi Clive James tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlar asosida ishlab chiqilgan. Bt-makkajo'xori genetik modifikatsiya qilingan bo'lib, uning tarkibiga *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) bakteriyasining geni kiritilgan. Bu gen makkajo'xorini zararkunandalardan himoya qiluvchi toksin ishlab chiqaradi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, Bt-makkajo'xori zararkunandalarga chidamli bo'lib,

hosildorlikni oshirish va pestitsidlar qo'llanilishini kamaytirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi [2].

GMO mahsulotlarining inson organizmiga ta'siri turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarda o'rganilgan. Masalan, Bernstein o'z tadqiqotlarida GMO mahsulotlari allergik reaksiyalarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkinligini ko'rsatgan. Ba'zi hollarda, genetik modifikatsiya qilingan oziq-ovqatlar yangi allergenlarni paydo qilishi yoki mavjud allergenlarning darajasini oshirishi ehtimoli mavjud.[3] Bundan tashqari, Van den Eede (2004) GMO mahsulotlari antibiotiklarga chidamli bakteriyalarning rivojlanishiga sabab bo'lishi mumkinligini aniqlagan. Bu esa antibiotiklarning samaradorligini pasaytirish xavfini tug'diradi.[4] Shuningdek, Gilles-Eric Seralini (2012) tomonidan o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlarda GMO mahsulotlarini iste'mol qilgan kalamushlarda o'sma rivojlanganligi kuzatilgan. Biroq, ushbu tadqiqot natijalari ilmiy hamjamiyatda keng muhokamalarga sabab bo'lib, uning metodologiyasi tanqid qilingan [5].

GMO mahsulotlari bo'yicha ilmiy hamjamiyatning fikrlari ikkiga bo'lingan. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti GMO oziq-ovqatlari xavfsiz ekanligini bildirsa, AQSh Milliy Fanlar Akademiyasi GMO mahsulotlari va an'anaviy mahsulotlar o'rtasida inson salomatligiga ta'sir borasida sezilarli farq yo'qligini ta'kidlaydi. Shu bilan birga, Evropa oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi agentligi GMO mahsulotlarini sinchkovlik bilan tekshirish zarurligini qayd etgan GMO mahsulotlarining iqtisodiy va ekologik jihatlariga ham katta e'tibor qaratilgan. BMTning Oziq-ovqat va qishloq xo'jaligi tashkiloti GMO mahsulotlari oziq-ovqat tanqisligini kamaytirishi va hosildorlikni oshirish orqali global oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashga yordam berishini ta'kidlaydi. "Oltin guruch" loyihasi rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda bolalar o'rtasida A vitamini tanqisligidan kelib chiqadigan ko'rlik va boshqa sog'liq muammolarining oldini olishga xizmat qilishini qayd etadi. Shuningdek, Clive James o'z tadqiqotlarida GMO mahsulotlari zararli pestitsidlarga ehtiyojni kamaytirishini, bu esa atrof-muhitga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatib, dehqonchilik xarajatlarini pasaytirishga yordam berishini aniqlagan. [1,2]

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish kerak-ki GMO mahsulotlari oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlash, hosildorlikni oshirish va qishloq xo'jaligida kimyoviy vositalarni kamaytirish imkoniyatlarini yaratadi. Biroq, ularning inson salomatligiga uzoq muddatli ta'siri bo'yicha ilmiy bahslar davom etmoqda. Hozirgi kungacha o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar GMO mahsulotlarining zararli ekanligini to'liq isbotlamagan bo'lsa-da, allergik reaksiyalar, antibiotiklarga chidamlilik va metabolik o'zgarishlar ehtimoli mavjudligi ilmiy manbalarda qayd etilgan. Shu sababli, GMO mahsulotlari ustidan qat'iy nazorat o'rnatish va qo'shimcha tadqiqotlar olib borish kelajakda ushbu mahsulotlardan kelishi mumkin bo'lgan xavflarni oldini olishga xizmat qiladi.

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